

Comparative analysis of microplastic pollution in commercially relevant seafood across different geographical regions

IMP

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Aims

The aim of this study is to quantify MP contamination in commercially relevant seafood (clams, mussels, and shrimps) from different geographical regions and to identify the types and morphologies of MP using microFTIR analysis, while assessing potential health risks associated with microplastic transfer to humans through seafood consumption.

Introduction

Microplastic pollution is a growing concern, with seafood being a potential source of human exposure. This study investigates microplastic contamination in clams, mussels, and shrimps from different geographical regions. By using standardized methods, we aim to compare contamination levels and assess potential health risks for consumers.

Results

Material & Methods

Figure 1. Commercially Relevant Seafood: Shrimps, Clams, and Mussels

Figure 2. Alkaline (10 % KOH) and enzymatic (pepsin and pancreatin) and oxidative (15% H₂O₂) digestion of samples

Figure 3. Thermo Scientific™ Nicolet iN10 Infrared Microscope, with LN-cooled MCT detector.

Figure 4. Thermo Scientific™ OMNIC™ Picta™ Software for the iN10 MX FTIR Microscope.

Figure 5. The map of the interrelationship among market location and physicochemical properties of MP identified in clams, mussels, and shrimps (size, polymer type and shape).

Polymer composition of MP

Polymer identification compared across different geographical regions

Frequency of MPs in shellfish

Figure 6. PCA analysis for microFTIR-based the abundance of MPs (MPs/g), tissue mass, MPs size (length & weight) and density of samples collected from the markets in Korea, Belgium and Croatia.

Score plots:
A) species trends
B) region trends
C) different MP types plot
D) loading plot describing the model direction/importance of variables.

Summary

- MP were identified in 43.3% of individually analyzed animals (n_{total}=190)
- Shrimps showing lowest abundance of MP/g of edible tissue
- Nonspecific accumulation tendency regardless of geographical origin or polymer type,
- Tissue mass and number of MPs/g are negatively correlated variables (number of MPs/g decrease with increase of tissue mass) - data does not support the bioaccumulation or biomagnification of MPs
- MPs width and length are variables negatively correlated with number of MPs per individual, suggesting that with increase of MPs accumulation their size is smaller